

DEVELOPING STUDENTS' VOCABULARY THROUGH INSIDE AND OUTSIDE CLASSROOM LEARNING

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Annotation: The purpose of this study is to show the importance and role of increasing students' vocabulary knowledge in the classroom and outside the classroom, and to consider the strategies used in the process of increasing their vocabulary. It presents useful approaches to practice based on the results of my research and the effective influence of the process of inside and outside learning, which affects the development of vocabulary in the educational process.

Key words – The classroom, inside learning, classroom-based subject, outside classroom learning, pedagogical tool, community-based development project.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi sinfda va sinfdan tashqarida talabalarning so'z boyligini oshirishning ahamiyati va rolini ko'rsatish va ularning so'z boyligini oshirish jarayonida qo'llaniladigan strategiyalarni ko'rib chiqishdir. Tadqiqot natijalari va ta'lim jarayonida lug'atning rivojlanishiga ta'sir qiluvchi ichki va tashqi ta'lim jarayonining samarali ta'siriga asoslangan amaliyotga foydali yondashuvlarni taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar - sinf, ichki ta'lim, sinfga asoslangan mavzu, sinfdan tashqari ta'lim, pedagogik vosita, jamiyatga asoslangan rivojlanish loyihasi.

Аннотация: Целью данного исследования является показать важность и роль увеличения словарного запаса учащихся на уроках и вне занятий, а

также рассмотреть стратегии, используемые в процессе увеличения их словарного запаса. В ней представлены полезные подходы на практике, основанные на результатах моих исследований и эффективном влиянии процесса внутреннего и внешнего обучения, которое влияет на развитие словарного запаса в образовательном процессе.

Ключевые слова – Класс, внутреннее обучение, предмет в классе, обучение вне класса, педагогический инструмент, проект развития на уровне сообщества.

I. INTRODUCTION

As a result of the reforms carried out in our country, the education system has been radically reformed, the educational process has been adopted and put into practice in accordance with global educational standards and national values, as well as state educational standards aimed at integration of education. Tasks such as "training of modern personnel who know several foreign languages in our country, conducting research on foreign languages, improving the methodology of language teaching" are set. In this regard, due to the fact that today the world science is developing not within a single discipline, but in an interdisciplinary direction, in our country there are problems such as teaching foreign languages and language, their relationship to each other, the impact of these issues on society. Learning is important. In the 21st century, the development of foreign language skills of young people and the exchange of skills in the field of interstate pedagogy are important factors in the growing interest for developing learners' developing skill and its depends on inside and outside classroom learning process.

The scientific work is a scientific report aimed at finding answers to the following problems and questions:

- What is the need to develop vocabulary?
- How is the process of inside and outside the classroom learning organized?

- What is the inside and outside learning process?
- What are the ways students can increase vocabulary inside and outside the classroom?

To answer these questions, the researcher examines various works on the topic and conducts experiments with students.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The classroom is the place where teachers actively create the conditions for learning weaving together knowledge of the discipline or field of knowledge; ways of working in that discipline or field; their knowledge of how to make the various concepts, content and procedures in that discipline or field learnable.¹ The inside learning is a learning process that is typical of the traditional teaching method and is learning with a sense of classroom environment and responsibility. For example, the equipment and devices available in the classroom, posters, teaching aids, the location of the teacher and the teacher, the decoration of the classroom with equipment in the prescribed requirements, etc. are all processes reminiscent of the classroom. Inside classroom learning is the acquisition of knowledge using classroom and classroom-based subjects, based on textbooks, artificial templates, visual aids, handouts, and sometimes the subject and vocabulary being studied. The imaginary worlds of students are used in the framework.

Outside classroom learning is the use of places other than school for teaching and learning. It's about taking kids and young people out, giving them challenging, exciting, and diverse experiences to help them learn. Places can belong to an activity or workshop, but the goal is the same no matter where the extracurricular learning takes place. It is about giving students a real-world learning experience to succeed in extracurricular life. The use of outside

¹ <https://www.google.com/search?q=inside+classroom+learning&rlz=>

classroom learning is well known as an effective pedagogical tool in building a diverse and sustainable education. It has been shown to increase learning outcomes, motivation, physical activity, and social behavior among pupils and students (Fägerstam, 2012, Mygind, 2007). Extracurricular learning includes many practices, from excursions to monuments and natural sites, to field trips, field work, and community-based development projects (Rikkinson et al., 2004). However, in European education systems today, extracurricular education is largely understood as an adjunct to traditional education and is traditionally added randomly to places related to the external environment, such as environmental education.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design. The research design applied in this research was Quasi-experimental which applied the non-equivalent Control Group Design with Pre-test and Post-test. Sugiyono (2014) stated that in this design, there were two groups which were taken randomly. In order to determine the results of scientific work, experimental tests are conducted on a regular basis for a pre-selected group, as well as entrance and exit tests at the beginning and end of the quarter, as well as for other groups, which did not conduct experiments at all. “Input” and “output” tests are performed and the results are compared.

B. Participants. Traditionally, English classes are taught in 2 groups when the number of students exceeds 20, and we also decided to organize research work with 2 groups in two different ways, with 1 group from each group selected for the experiment. Half of the classes were organized in the traditional style, inside the classroom, and the second part of the group was conducted in order to improve the vocabulary on the same topics with the outside classroom approach.

C. Analysis

During the question and answer session with the students, it was found that there was a need to develop their Vocabulary knowledge. The students' responses

led to the following conclusions:

- High need for vocabulary formation due to the need for vocabulary richness in any learning process
- The effective use of different methods in the process of indoor classroom learning stimulates the development of the necessary vocabulary by increasing the interest of students
- The methods and techniques used by the teacher should be within the scope of the topic and should be applied within the context of interest and age
- There was a need for a wider application of the outdoor classroom learning approach in the educational process, which would allow students to expand their vocabulary and use the appropriate range of word structures in different environments.

D. Result

The research work refers to both a qualitative and a quantitative type of research. The analysis of the data is based on numerical method. The results of the progress tests and the final test are reported in numbers and expresses in graphs.

Figure 1. Analysis of students developing vocabulary knowledge on approaches: inside and outside classroom learning processes

Almost all chart results also show that each topic is important in terms of the circle being studied, and whether they are in-classroom or outdoor classroom learning, the result is related to the environment in which it is created and its subject matter, and we were convinced that a slightly different inside classroom learning approach would develop a more vocabulary than an inside classroom approach.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In conclusion, there is also logic in taking English learners as the subject of this research, which is assessed by the fact that they need a vocabulary knowledge. Those who are just starting to learn a language, they always feel the need to take directions and they need a comfortable place to study, which is a classroom, and high level students can learn the language on their own. At the same time, students have a high need for both classroom and extracurricular learning processes, and their memories are based on reality, so as an outcome of the research, they have an alternative to the relevant outdoor classroom learning, for this cases areas were selected, additional areas are a phenomenon dependent on the learner himself, and can form a regular vocabulary in any area. In general, Vocabulary richness is very important for English learners, and not only indoor classroom learning strategies but also outdoor learning should be considered in its formation.

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